

Cryptocurrency Analysis using AI

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This is to certify that the project titled “**Cryptocurrency Analysis using AI**” is the genuine work carried out by **Rehman Sadaqat, Aiman Khan**, student of BSCS of Computer Science Department, Lahore Garrison University, Lahore during the academic year 2018-22, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Bachelor of Computer Science and that the project has not formed the basis for the award previously of any other degree, diploma, fellowship or any other similar title.

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DECLARATION

This is to declare that the project entitled “**Cryptocurrency Analysis using AI**” is an original work done by undersigned, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree “Bachelor of Science in Computer Science” at Computer Science Department, Lahore Garrison University, Lahore.

All the analysis, design and system development have been accomplished by the undersigned. Moreover, this project has not been submitted to any other college or university.

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DEDICATION

We would like to dedicate this project to our parents, specifically our mothers whose continuous support and dedication has led us to this point.

We would also like to dedicate this project to our seniors and fellows and our supervisor who helped us along this path.

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List of Abbreviation

FB	Firestore
DB	Database
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CC	Cryptocurrency
OP	Open Price
TS	Time Stamp
API	Application Programming Interface
CBA	Component Based Development
CGP	Candle Graph Prediction
BTC	Bitcoin
ETH	Ethereum
XRP	Ripple
NLTK	Natural Language Toolkit
AS	Android Studio
VS	Visual Studio

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Abstract

Cryptocurrency is on the peak of popularity since the rise of Bitcoin and the term has been affecting our daily lives. A lot of people are struggling to understand the concept while the others wonder how it would be profitable to them.

The project “Cryptocurrency Analysis using AI” aims to provide an application that can predict the price of cryptocurrencies in a narrative format as well as show past record graphs of the cryptocurrency. The application also aims to provide a centralized i.e., global chat system to users for better interaction among the users of the application. Our targeted audience are the people who wants to get a know-how of trading in respective of how the community views the cryptocurrency. For this purpose, we have chosen Reddit. According to a survey, Reddit is the most favorite social media application for crypto-users. Our application gets public posts from Reddit with the keywords of our chosen cryptocurrencies and analyses the post on the parameters of 5 pre-trained lists of Very Positive, Positive, Neutral, Negative, Very Negative and shows the influence of those posts in terms of prediction.

We also choose to show the graphs of the cryptocurrency that we choose i.e., Bitcoin, Ethereum and Ripple in a candle graph. Now there is only one other website (with no android application) who is plotting a stock graph on the parameters of High, Low, Open, Close and Volume. Our api requests data from that website and we plotted the candle graph since candle graphs are the easiest and most readable form of graphs, with a time interval of 24 hours because of the fact that we are using the Low and Close factor in our data.

The three working modules of our application i.e., Chats, Graphs and Predictions are working smoothly and aims to provide not only the community point of view but also to raise the awareness of how the price of crypto-currency is going. Our application is not based on the capsule concept of trading but rather uses a simple approach of how the currency is doing and how the community is going to affect it.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Prycto is an Android application designed for people who are interested in Cryptocurrency trading and investment. This application will help them in Cryptocurrency analysis and prediction and also show them the candle graph of the three of the top trending Cryptocurrencies i.e., Bitcoin, Ethereum, and XRP. It is an Android Application for cryptocurrency investors and traders which it will predict the value of cryptocurrency after analysing the market value of the trending cryptocurrency along with the predictions.

Prycto shows the predictions of the cryptocurrency descriptively on fine-grained parameters of sentiment analysis i.e., very positive, positive, neutral, negative, and very negative. The stock market of the cryptocurrency would have data collected based on open price, close price, high price, low price, and volume of the cryptocurrency which would be displayed using a candle chart. It also offers a chat module for different users to communicate with each other in a centralized manner. Users can share plans and strategies on when and how to trade in cryptocurrency and share knowledge in a centralized manner.

Prycto is the only application that offers the prediction designed on the Reddit posts as Reddit is the most popular platform out there for crypto-influencers. By predicting whether the cryptocurrency would have a positive, negative or neutral impact, we acknowledge and implement the social factor of the rise-fall of the coin.

1.1. Intended Audience and Reading Suggestions

While the report is written for a more general audience, it highlights all the stakeholders in the project. Those could also include Software Developers, Data collectors, Project Consultants, and Users. While the is primarily written for the Team Evaluators, the document also highlights

the basis of the Cryptocurrency Prediction and its parameters which could also interest the investors. This document doesn't require to be read in a sequence. Readers are allowed to jump to the section of their own choice.

1.2. Organizational Report

- Chapter 1 & 2 (INTRODUCTION & PROBLEM STATEMENT)

This section deals with the overview of the project, the problem to be solved behind it, and what lead to the implemented solution. It also deals with the goals and objectives that are to be achieved and defines the typing structure of the report document to help the reader better understand.

- Chapter 3 (SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION)

Readers interested in the initial blueprint of the end product should consult this section, which covers the initial goals, functions, and constraints of the application.

- Chapter 4 (METHODOLOGY)

This section includes a detailed description of the tools and technologies used. It discusses the software, hardware, and communication interactions with the UI and the basic requirements to them.

- Chapter 5 (DETAILED DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE)

This section covers the features of the application as well as its integration with the sentiment analysis results and the candle graphs of the market trends along with the chat module. These modules are explicitly defined with detailed descriptions, figures, and requirements.

- Chapter 6 & 7 (IMPLEMENTATION, TESTING AND RESULTS)

This section deals with how the product was structured, how it was tested, and what were the results.

- Chapter 8 (CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK)

This chapter deals with the conclusion of our project and how the project would be improved. What factors could be modified and how is the plan to get it done?

Chapter 2

Problem Definition

2.1. Background

As we have discussed before in great detail that cryptocurrency is the future. When we are talking about the fact that cryptocurrency is going down or has a negative trend, we are generally talking about cryptocurrency w.r.t trading. With all the new 5G technologies, that are implementing a centralized blockchain framework in e-wallets, cryptocurrency sure has an undeniable future. It would be good to have an application on hand that is neither conceptual like Binance nor requires any additional knowledge of cryptocurrency for handling i.e., a perfect app for beginners.

2.2. Problem Statement

A lot of people are hesitant for diving into advanced applications for trading without any know-how of it. Hence, we have devised an application that although doesn't allow trading but shows the historical data and uses sentiment analysis to predict the currency. One of the main reasons for this application is that no existing application uses the trends of a specific community but focuses on the market trends for prediction.

2.3. Proposed Solution

We have designed our idea on the above-mentioned basis. Although our application is focusing on the trading part and is leaning toward the volume of the 3 chosen crypto-currency, the main idea is to develop a knowledgeable application as well as an application that takes the point of view of the general public in comparison.

Our proposed plan is to develop an android application that portrays the candle graphs of the past volume of a selected cryptocurrency. The android application should also perform the sentiment analysis by applying NLP on Reddit posts and give predictions on those trends. The application should also offer a chat functionality so that users can communicate with each other to discuss plans, and strategies and share knowledge.

Software Requirement Specification

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose

Cryptocurrency prices are difficult to forecast due to price volatility and dynamism. Around the world, there are hundreds of cryptocurrencies that clients use. However, due to the unforeseen changes within the crypto industry, it is impossible to predict the perfect time with accuracy, considering all the affectable factors. *The purpose is to emphasize and improve the new investors in the cryptocurrency industry to make better choices. By implementing Machine Learning or Deep Learning Algorithms, we will be defining an NLP model for the highest output. We will also be doing web scrapping on news/Twitter/Reddit trends and giving predictive signals for trading based on the result in the android application.* The integration of cryptocurrency trading w.r.t web scrapping will greatly increase the chances of the predicted value being near the actual value. To provide human-friendly interaction, the model will be integrated into a mobile application. The functioning of this android application will revolve around a user registering himself and could see the stocks related to the cryptocurrency of his choice. On the data collected in real-time and predictions made upon it, the application will give signals to the user to engage in buying/selling of the cryptocurrency.

1.2. Document Conventions

Key sentences related to a specific section are written in *Black Bold with Italic*.

Bold is used to refer to the keywords of a specific section.

BOLD typeface is used to indicate the User Interface i.e., menus, buttons, commands, options, etc.

Italic is used to indicate the second level priority among the list of priorities which indicates its importance in the feature and requirement.

UPPERCASE indicates that the following paragraph is solely defined in terms of the following keyword and is not related to anything specific but the whole document.

1.3. *Intended Audience and Reading Suggestions*

While the Software Requirement Specification (SRS) is written for a more general audience, it highlights all the stakeholders in the project. Those could include Software Developers, Data collectors, Project Consultants, and Users. While the SRS is primarily written for the Team Evaluators, the document also highlights the basis of the Cryptocurrency Prediction and its parameters which could also interest the investors. This document doesn't require to be read in a sequence. Readers are allowed to jump to the section of their own choice. Below is a brief overview of each part of the section.

- Part 1 (INTRODUCTION)

This section deals with the overview about the project, the problem to be solved behind it and what lead to the implemented solution. It also deals with the goals and objectives that are to be achieved and defines the typing structure of the SRS document to help the reader in better understanding.

- Part 2 (DESCRIPTION)

Readers interested in detailed description of the end product should consult this section, which covers the primary goals, functions and constraints of the application.

- Part 3 (EXTERNAL INTERFACE REQUIREMENTS)

This section includes the User Interface in detail. It discusses the software, hardware and communication interactions with the UI and the basic requirements to them.

- Part 4 (SYSTEM FEATURES)

This section covers the features of the application as well as its integration with the web scrapping results and the predicted results from applying the Machine Learning and Deep Learning Models. These features are explicitly defined with detailed descriptions, priorities and requirements.

- Part 5 (NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS)

This section deals with the requirements that are not required to run the application but are considered to be in-effect with the business and development ethics.

1.4. *Product Scope*

The scope of this project mainly focuses on the traders that are involved in cryptocurrency trading. This project will allow us to apply a Deep Learning or a Machine Learning Model to the data and choose a model to scrap. We will also be doing web scrapping (news/Twitter/Reddit posts) for sentiment analysis to project the new descriptive prediction. Based on our work, those predictions could help the user to buy or sell the cryptocurrency.

2. Overall Description

2.1. *Product Perspective*

It is a new self-contained product that relies on predicting the price of a cryptocurrency. The end product will be available to the user. The application will collect real-time data on cryptocurrencies and predict the price of the cryptocurrency on the basis of community views. The data collected will be buying and selling the respective cryptocurrency and integrating the results of web-scraping with it. The web scraping will be done on fine-grained parameters of sentiment analysis i.e., *very positive, positive, neutral, negative, and very negative*. The stock market of the cryptocurrency would have data collected based on *open price, close price, high price, low price, and volume* of the cryptocurrency. The parameters are discussed as follows:

Table 1. Extracted Parameters for Graph

PARAMETERS	DESCRIPTION
Open Price	The opening price of the currency at that day
Close Price	The close price of the currency at that day
High Price	The highest price of the currency that day
Low Price	The lowest price of the currency that day
Volume	Volume of the currency that is being traded that day

Figure 1. Functional Flow of Product

2.2. Product Functions

The function of the end-product includes gathering real-time data on the cryptocurrency based on the parameters of the Crypto Currency Market defined in the figure. After collecting the data, another data set based on the parameters of Web Scrapping will be integrated with the previous data and the defined models of Machine Learning, Deep Learning or LSTM will be applied. The result will then be sent to the application where it will be shown. A community feed will also be developed in the application for the user to interact with the community.

Figure 2. Class Diagram of Product

2.3. User Class and Characteristics

The different types of user classes of this project could vary from crypto-investors to crypto analysts. There is no before-hand knowledge required to be a user of this app. The minimal knowledge of crypto-currency required was eliminated by introducing the community feature within the application to assure the best experience for the user.

All the users of this application fall only in one class i.e., Crypto Traders. The User can register himself and can see the stocks predicted of his cryptocurrency. Based on these predictions, the

user will get Red/Green signals to trade in the currency or not. The User can also interact with other traders in a community section.

To further enhance the application, we divide the data into two sets i.e., the users who invest based on the app's prediction results and the users who just check out the results (which we refer to them as noise users) They complicate the performance data of the application so when analyzing the application usage, we omit them from the data to further enhance the accuracy of the performance of the end-product. Ultimately, even though the application does belong to the domain of Cryptocurrency, it doesn't limit its users. The application also doesn't require additional knowledge to operate.

2.4. Operating Environments

The end product is an Android application that will run on the latest versions of Android. The requirements include an internet connection to get real-time data about the cryptocurrency. The application does not require any additional hardware to execute successfully. A cellphone with the latest version of Android and a working internet connection are the basic requirements. Android Studio will be used to integrate the model we have worked on while the data on the model will be implemented by TF Lite Model Maker.

2.5. Design and Implementation Constraints

The constraint of this application, as discussed in the previous section, is that it requires a stable internet connection for the application to run. The application is not available for offline usage. The application will be designed in Android Studio SDK and Firebase will be used as a database. Java will be the primary language of the application.

2.6. User Documentation

Since the application requires minimal knowledge about cryptocurrency, the sole focus would be on the User Interface of the application. The UI will be designed to make it as user-friendly as possible. A tutorial would be shown when the user first downloads the application to make sure that he is familiar with the fragments of the application i.e., Graphs, Signals, and

Community Icon. A user would be able to choose whether he wants to watch the tutorial or not. A tutorial would be toast-based.

2.7. *Assumptions and Dependencies*

The application has the following **ASSUMPTIONS**:

1. Users should know how to use a cell phone.
2. The UI will be English-based so the User must know English to understand the application.
3. Users should have a basic knowledge of cryptocurrency if they are to invest.
4. The user should have the latest version of Android and a stable internet connection.

The application has the following **DEPENDENCIES**:

1. A slow Internet Connection will reduce the gathering speed of real-time data.
2. The application might not be available on the Google Play Store for the older versions of Android.

3. External Interface Requirements

3.1. *User Interface*

The User Interface of the Android Application will mainly focus on being interactive and simple. The best possible layout for this would be a Relative layout. The main screen would ask the user to enter two names i.e., USERNAME and PASSWORD. The user would have the option to either LOG IN if his account already exists or SIGN UP in case of a new user. Both buttons would lead us to different screens. SIGN UP would lead to screening A where the user would enter his credentials and login would lead to screen B where the User will have options to either enter the stock section or the community. From the Home Screen, the user can swipe back and forth into either of the sections i.e., STOCKS and CHATS. User can Check the STOCKS SCREEN where they can check the highlights of trading and in the CURRENCY section, he gets to choose their favored cryptocurrency and they can see the predictions of that specific currency. Due to the app still being in its initial phases, the blueprint has been decided as follows:

Figure 3. Initial Blueprint of Application

3.2. *Hardware Interfaces*

As the application gathers real-time data and applies different algorithms in it to process the result, the application relies heavily on software. Therefore, is no hardware requirement except a working cellphone with stable internet and the latest Android Version. However, it is recommended to have any Android Version after Android 4.2. A minimum of 512 MB RAM is also required; however, 2 GB is recommended for the smooth working of the application.

3.3. *Software Interfaces*

Since the end-product is a mobile application, it relies heavily upon software interfaces and components. We will be using Android as an Operating System. We will also be implementing ML libraries such as Keras and using Android Studio to integrate the results into the application. We will also be applying Deep Learning Models, LSTM, ANN. The main Language of the Software will be Java/Python. Tools i.e., TF LITE MODEL MAKER and ANDROID STUDIO are the highlights of our product.

3.4. *Communication Interfaces*

The user would need to register via email and SMTP would be used as a standard protocol. Firebase's real-time database connection would use HTTP v1 which is the most up-to-date and secure transition protocol. JSON will be used with HTTP(S) by using the google-gson library. The main communication interface is the internet via which all software components would be connected and real-time data would be gathered.

4. System Features

4.1. *User Registration*

4.1.1. **Description and Priority**

User must enter a username for the first time when opening the application. That username is in alphanumeric and allows a certain 25-character limit. User can use its real name or can forge a decoy name. Once entered, the data is stored in the cache and user won't need to enter name on every access.

Priority: High

4.1.2. **Stimulus/Response Sequences**

Use Case Number: U1

Use Case Name: Registration

Actor Name: User

Description: To register yourself

Stimulus: User requests to register itself with the application.

Response: The Sign-Up Page will be showed where User have to enter his user-name.

4.1.3. Functional Requirements

REQ-1: User must enter a username.

REQ-2: User have downloaded the application and is connected to an internet connection.

4.2. *Log In*

4.2.1. Description and Priority

After signing up, user will have to Login the application via his credentials to go to the Home Screen. If there is already an account, Home Screen would be the first screen to be showed to the user. If the user is not willing to do this step, he would not be able to use the application.

Priority: High

4.2.2. Stimulus/Response Sequences

Use Case Number: U2

Use Case Name: Login

Actor: User

Description: To authenticate yourself

Stimulus: User requests to use the application.

Response: The Login Page will be showed where User have to enter his User Name and Email to go to the Home-Screen.

4.2.3. Functional Requirements

REQ-1: User have successfully signed-up on the application.

4.3. *Chat Box*

4.3.1. **Description and Priority**

The chat box will be one of the two modules available on the home screen. The User will be able to chat with other users in a global chat box. The User will also be able to private chat with any of the other users by entering the username in the chat box.

Priority: **Medium**

4.3.2. **Stimulus/Response Sequences**

Use Case Number: U3

Use Case Name: Chats

Actor: User(s)

Description: To communicate with others.

Stimulus: User wants to chat with other user(s).

Response: User can interact freely within the Global Chat section.

4.3.3. **Functional Requirements**

REQ-1: Display **TYPE YOUR MESSAGE HERE** in the text view.

REQ-2: Compatible with dark mode

4.4. *Visualizations*

4.4.1. **Description and Priority**

The visualizations will involve the data gathered from applying the 5 parameters as discussed and presenting it in a form of candle graph. User will also be able to choose and see the predicted graph of his choice of cryptocurrency.

4.4.2. Stimulus/Response Sequences

Use Case Number: U4

Use Case Name: Crypto currency Predictions

Actor: User

Description: View Predicted Results

Stimulus: User wants to view the predictions about the cryptocurrency.

Response: User can see a Stocks Option on the Home Screen. Stocks would present a generalized prediction of cryptocurrency.

4.4.3. Functional Requirements

REQ-1: User must be connected to internet for real-time data gathering.

REQ-2: TBD

5. Other Non-functional Requirements

5.1. Performance Requirements

The performance of the Application hanging out there by its responsive time, time to wrap up the given obligation. For instance, when an application is made to fire up it shouldn't require over 3 seconds to stack the beginning screen. Correspondingly it ought to be ensured that the application will not block the client's Input. The Cryptocurrency Prediction application would be reliable to get most likely accurate results but not the exact result as there is not any model have made any result 100% accurate. The application would be fast as per international performance requirements. The crash won't happen in the application as it is one the best performance of the application to run without tripping.

5.2. Safety Requirements

Security requirements subtleties (SRS) are focal points that portray every fundamental prospering end that ought to be performed by a security instrumented structure (SIS). SRSs finish up both what flourishing cut-off points ought to be performed by development and how well those cut-off points ought to be performed. The application would be safe for the users. The quality of the software we'll be using would be good to make secure the data of the users.

5.3. Security Requirements

A security central is an affirmation of required security support that promises one of the different security properties of making PC programs is being satisfied. Security necessities are gotten from industry standards, genuine laws, and a foundation set to the side by past shortcomings. All the application information ought to be gotten and blended in with the least necessities so that it's shielded from the outside climate in addition to internal assault. Every user is concerned about their privacy and security and they should be. This application of ours would only get the required information for only work purposes, not more than this and not less than this. The sensitive data provided by a user would be confidential, secure, and available only for them.

5.4. Software Quality Attributes

It considers many specific things for having the best quality software which includes:

- **Availability:** It's a common plane of any reliable and working application to be available at any place without any problem. And this application of ours would be available for the user where they have a stable internet connection to get access to information for the prediction and get up-to-date.
- **Scalability:** It is also necessary for an application to cover and store the vast amount of updated data and stored data in it. As it is a prediction app, it would need and have a large amount of storage to store data that it would proceed to predict the values.
- **Performance:** It is one of the main qualities of software, without it software can't be used. This prediction application would be reliable because of its pace of prediction.

- **Interoperability:** Most of the apps are communicating through each other for the exchange of data. It requires the surety of data security by the user. During web scraping, there would be only the exchange of database or real-time data by our software for predictions. It would be safe for the user.
- **Testability:** testing is the main component of an application or any other software which is going to be this much important for the users and their (a kind of) financial security. This application would be first trained and then tested by the real-time data to have secure results.
- **Usability:** As the user of any cryptocurrency securing application, the user would be familiar with this app as it won't be that much different and difficult from other apps.
- **Security:** Every user is concerned about their privacy and security and they should be. This application of ours would only get the required information for only work purposes, not more than this and not less than this.
- **Functionality:** Every software should be functioning perfectly for its application to run faster and perform well. So, our application would be well trained and well tested for its best functionality.

5.5. Business Rules

A business rule is essential for the certifiable business that might organize framework movement. A standard should be seen, regardless else is proceeding. It routinely fuses evident norms or conditions for consistency. All clients need a veritable email address. It requires valid information from each individual in purchasing cryptocurrency so that they can log in to the prediction application with the same credentials. Their movements of selling and purchasing cryptocurrency would be recorded so our app can predict what they require or what they want to buy, would they be in profit and all.

Chapter 4

Methodology

1.1. Introduction

The project is an android application and IDE used is Android Studio. Although, Visual Code was also considered as a potential option. Flutter is used to design the front end while NLTK is used for statistical Natural Language Processing Language. Flask APIs is also used to make requests between modules. The waterfall development model is used for the application. The modules are further discussed below.

1.1.1. Flutter Overview

Flutter is an open-source UI framework made by Google. Its basic language is DART. Flutter allows you to create an application with a single programming language i.e., dart and one codebase. Flutter is a complete SDK that provides a complete set of widgets, integrated APIs and documentation. The programming language that flutter uses i.e., DART is a typical object-oriented language. Which focuses on the UI of the application. The advantages of flutter include its growing trends, maximum productivity and easy to learn and adeptness.

1.1.2. Supervised Learning

We have used the supervised learning approach for our project. The module of NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit) is used for semantic analysis approach. We derived a list of positive and negative words from pre-trained dataset and formulate it to classify the reddit posts that we get from the social community site. As suggested, a supervised approach will improve the accuracy of our descriptive statements.

1.1.3. NLTK Overview

NLTK is a platform with a collection of libraries that help us deal with the human language. We have used the toolkit to perform the most important factor of our project i.e., semantic analysis of reddit posts. It basically gets the posts from reddit, creates a bow and then under supervised learning, matches them with a pre-defined list. If the words of the reddit posts matches the keywords in defined lists, the descriptive prediction is shown on it.

1.1.4. Android Studio

Android Studio is a tool for building applications and is our preferable choice of IDE. We could also use VS Code for implementation. We chose the AS because of the fact that we have already worked in the said application. Although, the VS would implicate and provide more flutter-related plugins then android studio and is definitely a better choice.

1.2. Visualizations

Visualizations is the part of the application that shows the trends on 5 specific factors of OPEN, CLOSE, HIGH, LOW and VOLUME. The results of the visualizations are shown in a candle-graph. Our choice of visualization graphs is discussed further in the next section. The APIs are made which requests the server to send the data from a certain site to the application which in turn shows the graphs on the UI.

Figure 4a (left) and 4b (right)

1.3. Predictions

NLTK is used to import tokenizer within the scrapper file. After that, traditional population and lowercase words are transformed and implemented. A token is also initialized with the name counts which then counts with the words that are matched with the pre-trained data list that the nltk provides. With that respective, the descriptive prediction is shown.

Figure 5. NLP Overview

1.4. Methodology Overview

Figure 6. Component Diagram

Chapter 5

Detailed Design and Architecture

5.1 System Architecture

The android application is designed to run dynamically on all android devices. The requirements include an internet connection to get real time data about the cryptocurrency. The application does not require any additional hardware to execute successfully. A cellphone with the latest version of android and a working internet connection are the basic requirements. The different type of user classes of this project could vary from **crypto-investors to crypto analysts**. There is no before-hand knowledge require to be a user of this app. The minimal knowledge of crypto-currency required was eliminated by introducing the community feature within the application to assure best experience to the user.

All the users of this application fall only in one class i.e., Crypto Traders. The User can register himself and can see the stocks and predictions of Ethereum, Bitcoin and Ripple. On the basis of these predictions, user can choose to trade in the currency or not. The User can also interact with other traders in a community section.

To further enhance the application, we divide the data into two sets i.e., the users who actually invest on the basis of app's prediction results and the users who just check out the results (*which we refer to them as noise users*) They complicate the performance data of the application so when analyzing the application usage, we omit them from the data to further enhance the accuracy of the performance of the end-product. Ultimately, even though the application does belong to the domain of Cryptocurrency, it doesn't limit its users. The application doesn't require any additional knowledge to operate. The data will be ensured through Google Forms later and will be ensured in future work.

Figure 7. System Architecture

5.1.1 Architecture Design Approach

The architecture is a unit-class structure i.e., there is only one class of users. As discussed in the previous section, they all fall within the crypto-viewers. It is a generalized class that covers everyone from crypto-investors to crypto-influencers and crypto-analysts.

The chat is connected to the firebase server. The user opens the application and enters the username for the first time. The username is stored in the local memory and the user won't need to re-enter it every time. Although, for clearing all the app-data, user needs to clear cache from the settings of the mobile app. After the username is entered, which will primarily be used for communication, a new screen will appear which will represent the stocks and the prediction. The stocks are in a graphical plotting while the predictions are descriptive. The graph is plotted using the factors as mentioned in the srs document. However, the prediction is shown in a descriptive manner due to a user-friendly experience and to minimize the pre-requisite knowledge. The chats are designed as a global-view.

5.1.2 Architecture Design

Figure 8. Architectural Design

5.1.3 Subsystem Architecture

Figure 9. Subsystem Architecture

5.2 Detailed System Designing

There are 3 main components of this project

1. Stocks
2. Predictions
3. Chats

5.2.1 Classification

- Stocks are a part of the application that shows visualizes the historical data of the cryptocurrency.
- Predictions are made by analyzing the reddit community and shows whether crypto-trends are affecting the currency, positively or negatively.
- Chat module is a global communication interface within the application.

5.2.2 Definition

- Stocks provide a visualization of data on 5 factors namely, HIGH, LOW, OPEN, CLOSE and VOLUME. It enables the user to see the past performance of the cryptocurrency. Since, the main purpose of the application is to give the beginners of what is going on, it is necessary to show the historical performance of the cryptocurrency.
- Predictions are descriptive and based on 5 factors namely, VERY POSITIVE, POSITIVE, NEUTRAL, NEGATIVE, VERY NEGATIVE. It would enable even the general user to see whether a social platform has positive or negative about the cryptocurrency.
- Chat is a uni-communication system that would allow the open-users to chat, in an attempt to bridge the gap between people who are into crypto-trading or just there for knowledge.

5.2.3 Responsibilities

- The Stocks are one of the core components of idea the application is running on. It gives the historical data in a visualization form which helps the user to differentiate how far the cryptocurrency has come. The green signals show an uptrend and positive increase in value while the red signals show the downtrend and a decrease in value.
- Prediction shows the results in a descriptive way by analyzing reddit posts and sorting them in different fields.
- Chat allows the OPEN USERS to communicate with each other.

5.2.4 Constraints

The constraints of the application are limited to only a working internet connection.

5.2.5 Composition

There is no hardware component of the project. As software composition is concerned,

- Stocks are displayed on 5 factors i.e.,

Table 2. Grained Parameters for Extraction

PARAMETERS	DESCRIPTION
Open Price	The opening price of the currency at that day
Close Price	The close price of the currency at that day
High Price	The highest price of the currency that day
Low Price	The lowest price of the currency that day
Volume	Volume of the currency that is being traded that day

- Predictions defines the 5 factors namely, VERY POSITIVE, POSITIVE, NEUTRAL, NEGATIVE, VERY NEGATIVE.

5.2.6 Uses/Interactions

- Stocks are an independent variable and doesn't interact with any other component.
- Predictions are shown in a bottom view of the relative currency graph.
- Chat is an independent uni-structure module of the application.

5.2.7 Resources

As discussed before, the only requirement is a working internet connection.

Predictions require internet connection to gather data from coin market cap, a live generated dataset and show the results in a graph form.

5.2.8 Processing

Machine Learning models are used to revise the NLP on a pre-trained dataset. The login and views are designed in flutter. The V shaped model is due to the testing of each 3 phases individually.

5.2.9 Interface/Exports

Figure 10. Home Screen

Figure 11. Home Screen (dark mode)

Figure 12. Chatbox

5.2.10 Detailed Subsystem Design

Figure 13. Final Architectural Design with subsystem components

Chapter 6

Implementation and Testing

As discussed in chapter 4, the waterfall method is used to implement the whole structure of the android application. The graphs, predictions and chat are the basic modules of the application. Graphs use the following factors of HIGH, LOW, OPEN, CLOSE and VOLUME. A flask api is used to request the host site for the data of the graphs which then enables the request and send the data to the application. The same way, prediction gets the posts from Reddit and analyses them using NLTK framework and compare the words of the pre-trained lists provided to it. The prediction is basically on how the community views affect the price of the cryptocurrency, comparing with how the market trends are going.

6.1. Chat Testing

- User can send and receive texts, in a centralized system.

Figure 14. Chat UI

Figure 15. Chat Testing

6.2. Login Testing

- User need to enter Home Screen after login.
- User cannot proceed without a username.
- Alphanumeric username is allowed.
- Length of username can't exceed 25 characters.

```

134     },
135     );
136   }
137
138   Widget _buildRightSide() {
139     return SingleChildScrollView(
140       child: Padding(
141         padding: const EdgeInsets.symmetric(horizontal: 24.0),
142         child: Column(
143           mainAxisAlignment: MainAxisAlignment.max,
144           crossAxisAlignment: CrossAxisAlignment.stretch,
145           mainAxisAlignment: MainAxisAlignment.center,
146           children: <Widget>[
147             // AppIconWidget(image: 'assets/icons/ic_appicon.png'),
148             Text('Chat Name'),
149             Container(
150               height: 24,
151             ),
152             _buildUserIdField(),
153             // _buildPasswordField(),
154             // _buildPasswordField(),
155             // _buildForgotPasswordButton(),
156             Container(
157               height: 100,
158             ),
159             _buildSignInButton()
160           ],
161         ),
162       ),
163     );
164   }
165
166 }

```

Figure 16. Login UI

Figure 17. Login UI (left) and Error (right)

6.3. Home Testing

- User can scroll down easily on the screen.
- The zoom in and out are working on the graph.
- Reload button is working.
- Dark Mode is compatible.

```

73  @override
74  Widget build(BuildContext context) {
75    return Scaffold(
76      appBar: _buildAppBar(),
77      body: FutureBuilder(
78        builder: (ctx, snapshot) {
79          if (snapshot.connectionState == ConnectionState.done) {
80            if (snapshot.hasError) {
81              return Center(
82                child: Text(
83                  '${snapshot.error} occurred',
84                  style: TextStyle(fontSize: 18),
85                ),
86              );
87            } else if (snapshot.hasData) {
88              final data = snapshot.data as List<String>;
89              List<String> uniqueList = [];
90              for (String things in data) {
91                if (!uniqueList.contains(things)) {
92                  print(things);
93                  uniqueList.add(things);
94                }
95              }
96            }
97            final ValueNotifier<List<String>> thing =
98              ValueNotifier<List<String>>(uniqueList);
99            return ValueListenableBuilder<List>(
100              valueListenable: thing,
101              builder: (BuildContext context, List value, Widget? child) =>
102                _buildBody(value));
103          }
104        }

```

Figure 18. Home UI

Figure 19. Home Screen UI

6.4. Use Case Diagram

For testing purposes, we have used a use-case method. All the above said methods are tested on the interface. According to the use case diagram, User can;

1. Enter Username (for more detail, please refer to 6.1. Testing)
2. User can switch to dark mode on Home Screen.
3. User can reload the entire screen.
4. User can zoom in/out of the graphs.
5. User can view narrative predictions of the Reddit posts.
6. User can chat globally.

Figure 20. Use Case Diagram

Chapter 7

Results and Discussions

The use cases that were defined in the software requirement specification document were modified to the point to reach the goal of the application i.e., to make an educative as well as predictive application about cryptocurrencies. The application provides stock market data on the application as well as what the community does and how that factor influences that crypto standard. Starting of with the graphs part, our goal was to develop an android application that provides the data on 5 grained parameters of HIGH, LOW, OPEN, CLOSE and VOLUME. The coin market cap is already implementing the said graphs. We have further devised that graph for better understanding.

Table 3. Comparison between PRYCTO and other applications

	Binance	Crypto Forecast	Lambo Time	FRCST	Crypto GAG	US
Prediction	Market Users ✓	AI - Predictions Bad Resources Sentiment Analysis (Source: Twitter)	✗	Trading Bot (Basically a Trading app)	Sentiment Analysis (Source: None)	Sentiment Analysis (Source: Reddit)
Chats	Chat V5.0. (support chat)	✗	✗	✗	✗	Chat with other Users (No Support System)
Graphs	✓	✗	Present Change	Both Present & Past ✓	Past (Each day Before) ✓	Past (Each day Before) ✓
Market		✓	Selective Parameters (High - Low)	✓	✓	✓
News	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗

The above table clearly states the comparison between our application “US”(right-most) and the similar applications that are in the market. Our application is the only product that is using the sentiment analysis of reddit users as a predictor, partially similar to Crypto Forecast which is doing the sentiment Analysis based on tweets.

Our application provides a centralized chat system for a number of reasons, a new application, private chat module was included in future scope of this and the fact that our application is mainly designed to provide predictions as well as a interactor between the crypto-community where they can collectively share information about the dips.

Our application is designed to produce candle graphs for the reason that they are the most user-friendly graphs and require no knowledge to understand. The only application out there that are showing the graphs on these 5 parameters are the coin market cap, which is a website and our application, PRYCTO. The reason that we chose to present past day and wait 24 hours before the new update is that we also show how the cryptocurrency went on its closing price and it is essential to calculate closing price as well as lowest price to calculate the volume which is one of the gravest factors of the graph.

Table 4. Description of Extracted Features along their unit

Features	Explanation	Unit
Timestamp	Time of data collection from the time post is published on Reddit	The format of data is in dd/mm/yyyy
Open Price	Each day open price based on the timestamp	USD
High Price	Highest price per day records	USD
Low Price	Lowest price per day records	USD
Close Price	Final Price of a day	USD
Currency Volume	Exchange rate price turnover	USD

As shown in the recent table are the parameters of how the price is collected and then shown on the graph.

Follow is the comparison of how our application is better in handling and processing than others;

- A lot of applications are asking for premium subscription for users to chat.
- A lot of applications don't provide predictions and chats in a single application, that is better to use and without any confidential information.
- As the main point of our application is to attract people who wish to know about the cryptocurrency but are afraid to install or interact with an application due to privacy issues, data handling issues or find the applications out there difficult to trust. In Prycto, you can choose to communicate via real identity or a forged name. As we do not require any login at the moment and the chat is a centralized system, we do not have the constraint of real identities.

Chapter 8

Conclusion and Future work

8.1. *Conclusion*

Prycto is safer and more secure than other applications as it does not require any credentials to log in. The application allows you to work on it just by adding a username and you can access it without sharing your details. Prycto is for prediction after analysing the posts of the main three cryptocurrencies through the well-known application named Reddit. It will help the investors to analyse the value of the desired cryptocurrency which will help them to invest the money wisely and get profit from the right side.

The application does not require any personal information like other apps which ask for location, access to the gallery, phone, camera, messages, and even your wallet. Additionally, users can chat with other users around the globe having a secret identity (by adding a nickname instead of a real name) or by adding their real name as a username.

It allows the user to add the username of twenty-five data fields which includes alphabetic and alphanumeric letters, therefore a limited number count helps the user to write the original name or if they are writing a nickname, they can select a name within twenty-five letters. The global chat box allows the user to share their thoughts on the current analysis of cryptocurrency and news related to cryptocurrency which would help the users to be more aware of the market and each other's thoughts.

It provides the graphs which show the current market price of the desired cryptocurrency shown in the application. The graph has also the capability to show the market rate for more than one year which allows the user not to analyse but also to keep a record of the following cryptocurrency which helps the user to discuss the future of cryptocurrency more deeply. It also provides a one-word prediction instead of a whole paragraph which helps the user to understand the prediction without wasting a lot of time.

It also has the latest feature of Light mode and Dark mode, which attracts the user and also a good eye shield for day and night time. Hence, it is quite safe and sound to install and analyse the cryptocurrency and its prediction.

8.2. *Future work*

As cryptocurrency is growing and will become a future currency for any kind of trading like in metaverse or simply ordering pizza from pizza hut. Every up-to dated person is going to need a better application to get better predictions of cryptocurrency therefore, they can invest on the right side and don't have to bear the loss. The modifications we are going to start on the application to make it more reliable for the future. The Application does analysis and predicts the trending main three cryptocurrencies, we will add other cryptocurrencies in the future to make this app more reliable for other cryptocurrencies. The second thing we will be including in it would be supporting chat. We would try to add a customer care chat for the user it could be bot chat or human-to-user (depends on the popularity of the application). After that People who are going to know the predictions through the application, most probably are going to invest in cryptocurrency. That's why we will going to add a login and signup option for the ease of the user to stay connected with the global chat and there will be another option of signing up by Google Account or Phone Number. The person can always log out and get the predictions without logging in or signing up. Also, they can sell and purchase with the help of google pay, the cryptocurrencies presented in the application to fulfill their desire for investment if they sign up by google. And the application would be more secure for these requirements.

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